

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON SELF CURING CONCRETE

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Abstract

Building and sustaining global infrastructure to satisfy the future requirements of both industrialized and developing nations is essential for economic growth and enhancing living standards. The quality and effectiveness of concrete is essential for various infrastructures, including commercial, industrial, residential, and military buildings, as well as dams and power stations. Concrete is the most extensively produced material globally, with over 6 billion metric tons of it generated each year. The initial and life-cycle expenses significantly impact the development of infrastructure today. Numerous significant developments have occurred in concrete technology over the past fifty years. In recent times, the idea of internal curing in concrete has become more popular and is gradually moving from the lab to practical applications. As per the ACI 308 committee, internal curing is described as the process in which cement hydration takes place due to the presence of extra internal water that is separate from the mixing water.

Keywords: Concrete, Polyethylene glycol, water, curing

1. INTRODUCTION

The benefits of internal curing are numerous and include, increased hydration process and strength development, reduced autogenous shrinkage and cracking, reduced permeability. The impact of internal curing begins immediately with the initial hydration of the cement, so that its benefits are observed at ages as early as 2 days or 3 days. Internal curing is beneficial in low water-cement ratio (w/c) concretes because of the chemical shrinkage that accompanies Portland cement hydration and the low permeability of these materials. Since the water incorporated into and absorbed by the cement hydration products has a specific volume less than that of bulk water, a hydrating cement paste will imbibe water (about 0.07 g water/g cement) from available sources. While in higher w/c concretes, this water can be and often is supplied by external (surface) curing.

2. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

Advantages

- Increase relative humidity.
- Lower maintenance and higher performance.
- Reduce the equipment cost.
- Manpower cost saving.
- Shorter construction period.

Disadvantages

- Lower water-cement ratio.
- It is costly to compare the other concrete.

- Plastic shrinkage cracks may occur

3. SCOPE OF PROJECT

Scope of the study is to identify the effect of polyethylene glycol (PEG) on strength characteristics of self-curing concrete and also to evaluate influence of poly ethylene glycol on mechanical properties which are experimentally investigated. To study the strength properties of concrete made with curing compound i.e. polyethylene glycol as self-curing agent with that of concrete made from conventional curing. The major challenge in construction field nowadays is the lack of availability of water; this problem can be reduced to a greater extent with the introduction of self-curing concrete. Since self-curing concrete controlling the rate and extend of moisture loss from concrete during hydration. The chemicals should have abilities to reduce evaporation from solution and to improve water retention in ordinary Portland cement matrix

Objectives of project work

The main objective of this study is to find out the physical properties of hardened concrete with the curing agent and Fly ash also we have to find out optimum percentage of Fly ash will be used for improving the mechanical properties of concrete along with the economy.

- To study the effect of curing compound (PEG-400) on the strength properties of concrete.

- Concrete mixes are prepared based on different % of Fly ash.

To study the mechanical characteristics of concrete such as compressive strength, Flexural Strength and split tensile strength by varying the percentage of Fly ash from 10%, 15% and 20% by weight of cement for M25 grades of concrete.

Correlations and Designations

Proportion of Polyethylene Glycol & Fly ash Cement Properties Physical properties of Fine Aggregate (sand).

Table 1 Proportion of Polyethylene Glycol & Fly ash

Sr. No	Property	Results
1.	Particle Shape, Size	Round, below 4.75mm
2.	Fineness Modulus	3.44
3.	Silt content	3%
4.	Specific Gravity	2.60
5.	Surface moisture	Nil

Table 2 Cement Properties Physical properties of Fine Aggregate (sand)

Sr.No.	Description of Test	Results
01	Fineness of cement (residue on IS sieve size 90 micron)	4%
02	Specific gravity	3.15
03	Standard consistency of cement	32%
04	Setting time of cement: (IS 12269-1987) Initial setting time Final setting time	45 min, 275 min.

Working of the Proposed System

Three-phase brushless DC motors rely on electronic controllers to energize specific windings at precise moments, allowing for more efficient and reliable operation. The motor consists of a stationary part called the stator, which contains multiple coils of wire arranged in a specific pattern. These coils are also known as phases. The rotor is the rotating part of the motor and is composed of permanent magnets or electromagnets. The number of magnets corresponds to the number of phases in the stator.

Model Construction

There are 3 sets of coils wound around n-number of poles inside the stator; each set of coils is switched sequentially based on hall sensor feedback to rotate the motor. [7]

Motors Class

In- Runner Brushless DC Motor:

This type of BLDC motor has the rotating part(rotor) inside an assembly of electromagnet coils(stator). This brushless DC motor construction allows for heat dissipation through conduction since the stator coils are mounted on the motor's casing. An in- runner brushless DC motor attains peak speeds easily and is best for applications that require higher RPM characteristics. These motors often do not use many poles in the rotor. As a result, their performance reduces at lower speeds. [9]

Comparison of different circuits

Compared to traditional brushed motors, the cost of building a brushless DC motor is typically high. The

inclusion of pricey electronic controller circuits and occasionally sensors is primarily to blame for this.

CPM

The main use of mosfets is to control conductivity and the amount of electricity that passes through its source as well as drain terminals based on the amount of voltage applied across its terminals.

The type of field-effect transistor (FET) that is used most frequently is the metal-oxide semiconductor field-effect transistor (MOSFET, pronounced MAWS-feht). Based on the voltage applied to the gate terminal, they function as electrical switches and amplifiers, regulating the amount of electricity that can flow between the source and drain terminals. [12]

Digital Signal Processing

Given measurements that have been taken over time, Kalman filtering is a technique that produces estimates of some unknown variables. Kalman filters have proven effective in a variety of applications. Kalman filters have a straightforward structure and need little computational resources. [2]

System Design

The system comprises an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), a Motor Speed Controller (ESC) and a Microcontroller which helps it all to function. The system has peripherals like headlights and a Bluetooth module that sends live data to the phone (like speed, charging level, range, etc.).

System

The boards are divided into 2 PCBs, namely:

Control Board

MCU: The Microcontroller unit (MCU) serves as the central processing unit, orchestrating communication between various electronic components to ensure they function seamlessly as a unified system. The available Options are: Arduino ATMEGA 328, STM32 F4, STM32 F7 and STM32F103C8T6 Blue Pill [18] [19] [20].

Table 3 Key specifications of STM32 microcontroller

Voltage	6V
Frequency	77 MHz
GPIO pins	37
PWM pins	17
Analog Input Pins	14 (12-bit resolution)
I2C Peripherals	20
Peripherals 3	6
Peripheral 7	23
Timers	4(16-bit), 1
Flash Memory	64KB
RAM	24kB

The Specifications above exceed our requirements for BLDC motor and PID control. Additionally, the MCU has proven to be implemented successfully in segways and self-balancing vehicles. [20].

System Circuits

Control System IMU Circuit

The orientation and acceleration data is collected from the Inertial measurement Unit (IMU). The IMU is a single

chip that encompasses both a Gyroscope and an accelerometer. The measured position data is then sent to the STM32F103C8T6 microcontroller [18] [19] via an I2C bus. The Microcontroller then processes the data; this is done using the Kalman filter

4. CALCULATIONS

Polar moment of inertia of the EV is given by [1]: -

$$J_w = \frac{1}{2} m_w r_{bt}^2$$

$J_w = \text{Inertial moment of wheel}$

$$J_w = \frac{1}{2} m_w r_{bt}^2$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} (7)(0.14) = 0.0686 \text{ Kg. m}^2$$

Moment of Inertia of Vehicle As given by [1]: -

$$J_{bt} = \frac{1}{12} m_m (h_m + d_m^2) + \frac{1}{2} m_b r_c^2 - J_w$$

$$= \frac{1}{12} \times 70 \times ((1.6)^2 + 1 (0.21)^2) + \frac{1}{2} \times 14 \times (0.25)^2 - 0.0686 = 15.5349 \text{ Kg. m}^2$$

Center of mass as given by [4]: -

$$COG = \frac{m \times \frac{h}{2} + l_p \times 0.55 \times m_p}{m_{tot}}$$

$$= \frac{22 \times \frac{0.25}{2} + 1.6 \times 0.55 \times 70}{95} = 0.6773 \text{ m}$$

A minimum of 8.33A of current is required for the system to function without lag. With the motor requirement of 600W we need a 72v battery pack that can supply at least 8.33A of current continuously. We have chosen the INR18650P42A Lithium-ion cell by Moli cell for the construction of the battery.

Each cell being of 3.7v nominal and 4.2v maximum cell voltage, and capable of supplying 42A of continuous current. Each cell is rated for a capacity of 4.2Ah

Detailed Calculations

$$\text{Total Voltage} = T(0) = 72 \text{ v}$$

$$\text{Voltage per cell} = v_i = 3.75 \text{ v}$$

$$\text{Number of cells in series} = n_s$$

Now

$$\text{Total voltage} = \text{Voltage per cell} \times \text{Number of cells in series}$$

$$\text{So, Number of cells in series} = \frac{\text{Total Voltage}}{\text{Voltage per cell}}$$

$$n_s = \frac{77}{3.75} = 19.3$$

$$\approx 20 \text{ cells}$$

To be able to run the device for a distance of 50 Km and at a speed of about 25 km/hr.

$$v = \frac{d}{t} = \frac{50}{25} = 2 \text{ hrs}$$

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we detailed the process of designing an Electric Vehicle and thoroughly understood and elucidated the workings of various electronic components, including MOSFETs, gate drivers, BLDC motors, filters, IMUs, and PID controllers. We successfully interfaced these components with a microcontroller to receive hall sensor and IMU inputs, facilitating the operation of the gate driver circuit. Additionally, we designed and implemented this system on a custom-made PCB.

However, future work is necessary to fine-tune the PID controller and achieve stable self-balancing behavior, which we were unable to accomplish in this phase of the project.

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